

Exploring Novelistic Approaches of Nanostructured Lipid Carriers for Topical Drug Delivery

C. Haranath*, A. Lakshmi Hansika Yadav, S. Reshma Sana, P. Gayathri, K. Mounika, S. Abdul Muhsin

Department of Pharmaceutics, Raghavendra Institute of Pharmaceutical Education and Research (RIPER) -Autonomous, KR Palli cross, Chiyyedu (PO), Anantapur-515721, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Abstract- Nanostructured lipid carriers [NLCs] depicts an advanced drug delivery systems which enhances in improving the drug stability, controlled release, and targeted delivery for the treatment purpose. The solid lipid and liquid lipid forms NLCs elicit a unique amorphous feature that enhances drug loading and reduces dose dumping during storage. The small size of NLCs is especially beneficial for topical and transdermal patches which promotes intimate contact with skin, and helps in deeper drug penetration. The incorporation of biodegradable lipids and eliminating the usage of organic solvents make NLCs safer and more eco-friendly for therapy. Additionally, NLCs have exhibit enhanced drug delivery in ocular application also by overcoming the several barriers and enhance bioavailability. There are several preparation techniques used such as high-pressure homogenisation, and solvent injection, allow for precise control over size of the particle and making the NLCs adjustable for a range of drugs, including both hydrophilic and lipophilic compounds. Regulatory considerations require detailed insight of characterisation to evaluate consistent quality, while toxicity concerns are addressing through the selection of biocompatible materials used in the preparation of NLCs. This review describing the pharmacokinetic advantages, preparation methods and potential application of NLCs, and their role in improving the drug delivery effectiveness across therapeutic areas.

Keywords- Nanostructured Lipid Carriers, Drug Delivery, Biodegradable Lipids, Controlled Release, Skin Penetration, High-Pressure Homogenisation

I. INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology is currently being extensively utilized in drug delivery technology, allowing for both passive and active targeting through multiple administration routes. Its application in transdermal and topical drug delivery has opened new avenues for delivering pharmaceuticals through the skin[1]. Nanoparticles are colloidal particles with sizes of approximately 10–1000 nm. Nanocarriers are materials formed by dissolving or dispersing drugs within various types of nanoparticles, which can be categorized as either nanospheres or nano capsules. Nanoparticles are typically made from either polymer-based or lipid-based materials. Historically, Müller and Gasco around 1990s were firstly developed and nominated solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN) for the sake of avoiding organic solvents involved in preparation of polymeric nanoparticles. The Solid Lipid Nanoparticles are the first generation of lipid nanoparticles whereas the Nanostructured lipid carriers are the second generation of lipid nanoparticles. The NLC's are modified form of SLN's due to some drawbacks they possess. As this lipid nanoparticles which are colloid in nature provide some alternatives to other colloidal drug delivery systems such as liposomes, emulsions, and polymeric nanoparticles. This type of drug delivery systems is prepared by using some methods like high pressure homogenisation and ultrasonication methods other than using some toxic organic solvents. These SLN's and NLC'S are prepared by using some lipids which are biodegradable and physiological in nature[2].

SLNs are made of physiologically biocompatible excipients with solid matrices that can encapsulate drugs, providing protective loaded particles. The primary difference between SLNs and NLCs lies in their lipid composition: SLNs are formulated using solid lipids, while NLCs incorporate both solid and liquid lipids. The combination of solid and liquid lipids used to create NLCs remains solid at both room and body temperatures. While NLC consists of a mixture of specially blended solid lipid (long chain) with liquid lipid (short chain), preferably in a ratio of 70:30 up to a ratio of 99.9:0.1.

NLC can be loaded with hydrophobic or hydrophilic drugs with a wide range of drug-loading properties; the carrier material is biodegradable and exhibits low in vivo toxicity. These NLC's can be effective surface- modified to enhance their targeting abilities and improve drug delivery efficiency. These can involve the various ligands or polymers that can facilitate specific interactions with cellular receptors for targeted delivery. Moreover, NLC's exhibit organisational pattern for targeting and which is so advantageous for attaining the localised therapeutic effects. The physicochemical properties such as size, shape, surface charge and stability are necessary for the maintaining their performance and efficiency in drug delivery. NLC's have the ability to encapsulate both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs and also these will overcome the problems like degradation, solubility and bioavailability[3].

II. TYPES OF NLC'S

1. Type-I: Highly imperfect matrix

2. Type-II: Multiple types

3. Type-III: Amorphous type

A. Type-I

The NLC's are prepared by a lower concentration of liquid lipid [oil] is used in comparison to solid lipid. By combining the solid lipid and liquid lipids it forms [o/w] nano emulsion, cooling this mixture from molten state to room temperature which results in solid particles formation through a crystallization. This cause highly disordered and imperfect lipid matrix that provides space for the drug incorporation and results in amorphous drug structure.

B. Type-II

The NLC's a high concentration of oil is present. Phase separation takes place between two lipids during crystallization. At specific temperature, it forms tiny nano compartments which is oil in nature due to the miscibility gap. When lipids have low solubility for drugs, increasing the amount of liquid lipid in the lipophilic phase offers the benefits of a solid matrix, which prevents drug leakage, while the liquid lipid provides high solubility for lipophilic drugs.

C. Type-III

NLC, particles are formed through a controlled mixture of lipids, resulting in a solid that is not crystalline but rather in an amorphous state. It is essential to maintain this amorphous state[4].

The oral route is the most important and conventional method of drug administration. Unfortunately, oral drug delivery systems have many significant limitations, such as drug degradation in the gastrointestinal track (by enzymes, pH), pre-systemic metabolism or toxic side effects. One of the methods which could overcome problems associated with the oral route is transdermal drug delivery which is topical application. NLC possess numerous features that are advantageous for the topical route of application[5]. The small size of lipid nanoparticles promotes close contact with the stratum corneum, enhancing the penetration of the drug into the skin. Additionally, their occlusive properties contribute to increased hydration of the skin. Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) are specifically designed to enhance drug encapsulation efficiency, stability, and skin penetration. Comprising both solid and liquid lipids, NLCs form an amorphous structure that improves drug loading while minimizing expulsion during storage. These carriers create an occlusive layer on the skin, enhancing moisture retention and facilitating deeper drug permeation. By improving skin retention of the drug and limiting its systemic circulation, NLCs help reduce potential side effects[6].

The topical route of drug administration offers several advantages, including the avoidance of first-pass metabolism, lack of systemic drug absorption, facilitation of sustained drug delivery, and the ability to maintain a drug dosage regimen. This route is particularly beneficial for active molecules with short biological half-lives[7].

Administering drugs through the ocular route is challenging due to the eye's complex anatomical barriers, including the corneal, scleral, and retinal layers, as well as physiological factors like tear turnover, nasolacrimal drainage, and reflexive blinking. Due to their unique structure, nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) enhance corneal permeability, extend ocular retention, and thereby improve the bioavailability of the drugs they carry while minimizing systemic side effects. NLCs have been effectively used for delivering various drugs to the eye, including ciprofloxacin, amphotericin B, and dasatinib[8].

D. Advantages

- Control and targeted drug release.
- Greater loading capacity for certain drugs.
- Reduced water content in the dispersion.
- Prevention or minimization of drug expulsion during storage.
- Ability to load both lipophilic and hydrophilic drugs.
- Utilization of biodegradable and biocompatible lipids.
- Elimination of organic solvents.
- Cost-effective compared to polymeric and surfactant-based carriers.
- Simplified qualification, validation, and regulatory approval processes.
- Superior physical stability.

- Straightforward preparation and scalability.
- Improved benefit-to-risk ratio.
- Increased skin hydration and elasticity.
- Small particle size facilitates close contact with the stratum corneum.
- Enhanced drug stability.

E. Disadvantages

- Cytotoxic effects linked to the type of lipid matrix and its concentration.
- Potential irritation and sensitization caused by surfactants.
- The application and effectiveness for protein, peptide drugs, and gene delivery systems require further exploration.
- Stability of lipids[9],[10].

TABLE I

MATERIALS AND REQUIREMENTS FOR THE PREPARATION OF NLC

Solid Lipids	Beeswax, Carnauba wax 2442, Stearic acid Cetyl palmitate, Apifil® Cutina CP®, Dynasan® 116, Dynasan® 118, Precifac ATO Compritol® 888 ATO, Elfacos® C 26, Imwitor 900®, Precirol® ATO 5, Tristearin, Cholesterol, Palmitic acid
Liquid Lipids	Cetiol V, Miglyol® 812, Castor oil, oleic acid, Davana oil, Palm oil, Olive oil, Isodecyl oleate, Paraffin oil, propylene glycol dicaprylocaprate, linoleic acid, decanoic acid, Argan oil, coconut oil
Emulsifying agents	Pluronic® F68 (poloxamer 188), Pluronic® F127 (poloxamer 407), Tween 20, Tween 40, Tween 80, polyvinyl alcohol, Solutol® HS15, trehalose, sodium deoxycholate, Sodium glycocholate, sodium oleate, polyglycerol methyl glucose distearate, Tego®Care 450, Tween™80, Maquat® SC 18Maquat® BTMC-85%, Egg lecithin, soya lecithin, phosphatidylcholines, phosphatidylethanolamines, Gelucire® 50/13, Miranol ultra-32

III. METHODS FOR PREPARATION OF NLC

Various techniques for preparing nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) are documented in the literature, including high-pressure homogenization, microemulsion, probe sonication, solvent diffusion, solvent emulsification-evaporation, solvent injection/solvent displacement, and phase inversion. A summary of these methods is provided, with a detailed focus on the emulsification-solvent evaporation technique, which is regarded as an efficient, straightforward, and easily scalable approach.

A. High-Pressure Homogenisation

This method utilizes hot or cold high-pressure homogenization (HPH), depending on the drug's thermal stability. For thermostable drugs, hot HPH is applied at temperatures above the lipid melting points. In this process, a lipid phase consisting of solid and liquid lipids with lipophilic emulsifiers, and an aqueous phase containing hydrophilic emulsifiers and double-distilled water, are prepared separately and heated to a high temperature before mixing. This mixture is then homogenized using a high-shear homogenizer and may be sonicated to achieve a small and uniform particle size distribution.

Cold HPH, suitable for thermosensitive drugs, involves mixing the drug with the lipid phase at a temperature just above the lipid melting point, then rapidly cooling the mixture with liquid nitrogen or dry ice to quickly recrystallize the solid lipid particles. These particles are subsequently milled and emulsified in a cold aqueous phase using high-pressure homogenization, forming nanostructures of smaller size. This method offers advantages such as suitability for large-scale production, elimination of organic solvents, and enhanced product stability. However, high-pressure and temperature requirements can pose challenges, and incomplete homogenization may result in micro-particles rather than a uniform size distribution[11].

B. Microemulsion

In this method, melted lipids are combined with an aqueous phase containing a surfactant and co-surfactant to form either a water-in-oil (w/o) or oil-in-water (o/w) emulsion, depending on the proportions used. The emulsion undergoes vigorous mixing to reduce particle size to the micron range. A clear, thermodynamically stable microemulsion is then formed and subsequently dispersed in a cooled aqueous phase to further decrease particle size and produce NLCs. This technique is straightforward, cost-effective, reproducible, suitable for heat-sensitive drugs, and does not require specialized equipment or additional energy for NLC production. However, the need for high surfactant levels is a key limitation of this method.

C. High Shear homogenisation and Ultrasonication

High-speed stirring and ultra-sonication are widely used, cost-effective methods for producing solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) and nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs). High-speed stirring involves melting lipids, dissolving the drug, and mixing with a heated aqueous surfactant solution to form an oil/water emulsion, which solidifies upon cooling. Ultra-sonication, often following high-speed stirring, further reduces particle size by creating and collapsing bubbles. Combined, these methods yield narrow particle size distributions, though high temperatures can affect drug stability, and ultra-sonication may introduce metal contamination. While these methods avoid organic solvents, they require high surfactant levels and often result in broad size distributions without careful control[12].

D. Solvent Emulsification-Diffusion

The solvent emulsification-diffusion method, initially used for polymeric nanocarriers, was adapted to prepare SLNs and NLCs. This technique involves dissolving lipids and drugs in a water-saturated organic solvent (e.g., ethyl acetate), emulsifying in a stabilizer-containing aqueous phase, and diluting with water to induce lipid precipitation and form nanoparticles. The solvent is then removed by lyophilization or vacuum distillation. This method reduces exposure to high temperatures and stress, making it suitable for sensitive drugs and scalable. However, it requires substantial dilution and purification to eliminate residual solvents.

E. Solvent Emulsification-Evaporation

The solvent emulsification-evaporation method uses water-immiscible solvents (e.g., chloroform, dichloromethane) to prepare SLNs and NLCs by dissolving drugs and lipids, emulsifying in an aqueous phase, and then evaporating the solvent to induce lipid precipitation. This method is suitable for heat-sensitive drugs, yielding particles around 100 nm with narrow distributions. However, toxic solvents are required, resulting in a dilute suspension that needs further processing. Both the emulsification-diffusion and evaporation methods require additional purification to ensure residual solvents are at safe levels for biological use[13].

F. Phase Inversion

The phase inversion temperature (PIT) method produces nano emulsions, solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs), and nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) by inducing temperature-driven transitions between water-in-oil (w/o) and oil-in-water (o/w) emulsions. It utilizes non-ionic polyoxymethylene surfactants, which have a high hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB) at low temperatures that decreases as temperature increases. When heated above the PIT, surfactants favour w/o emulsions, while below the PIT, they form o/w emulsions. For instance, metronidazole-loaded NLCs prepared with monostearin and Capmul MCM achieved a particle size of under 300 nm and an encapsulation efficiency of around 40%. This method yields SLNs and NLCs with small particle sizes, narrow distributions, and good stability. However, it may result in low stability of nano emulsions and often requires multiple temperature cycles (e.g., three cycles between 60 and 90 °C[14].

G. Solvent Injection

The solvent injection method for producing solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) and nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs), first described by Schubert et al. in 2003, involves dissolving lipids and drugs in a water-miscible solvent, such as methanol or ethanol. An aqueous phase is prepared by adding an emulsifier to water or a buffer solution, and the organic phase is rapidly injected into the aqueous phase while stirring. Upon injection, the solvent diffuses into the aqueous phase, reducing droplet size and increasing lipid concentration, which creates supersaturated regions stabilized by emulsifiers. The emulsifiers also decrease interfacial tension, leading to the formation of small solvent-lipid droplets. Turbulence during solvent diffusion further breaks these droplets into smaller sizes. The energy released during solvent redistribution aids droplet division, resulting in the formation of SLNs and NLCs. Emulsifiers significantly affect particle size (PS) and distribution, with low concentrations effectively reducing PS. Generally, increasing emulsifier concentration decreases PS and polydispersity index (PDI) until a critical threshold is reached (0.5–1.5%), after which PS and PDI may increase. The rate of solvent diffusion into the aqueous phase is a critical factor influencing PS and size distribution[15].

H. Double Emulsion Technique

This method is primarily used to produce lipid nanoparticles containing hydrophilic drugs, addressing the issue of water-soluble components escaping into the aqueous phase, as seen in the microemulsion technique. In this approach, the drug is first dissolved in an aqueous solvent (the inner aqueous phase) and then dispersed in a lipid phase composed of molten solid lipid, liquid lipid, lipophilic surfactant, and lipophilic active ingredient, forming a primary water-in-oil (w/o) emulsion. Both the lipid and aqueous phases are maintained at the same temperature to ensure stability. A stabilizer is added to prevent drug loss to the external phase during solvent evaporation. The primary emulsion is then dispersed in a larger volume of surfactant-containing aqueous solution and subjected to sonication to create a double emulsion (w/o/w). Finally, the lipid nanoparticles are purified through ultrafiltration or solvent evaporation[16].

I. Membrane Contractor Technique

The membrane contactor technique is used to facilitate the interaction between two phases by maintaining their contact within a membrane system. In this process, a heated lipid phase above its melting point is placed in a pressurized vessel, where it permeates through ceramic membrane pores to form small droplets. Simultaneously, an aqueous phase flows tangentially within the membrane module, sweeping away the droplets as they exit the pores. As the system cools to room temperature, these droplets solidify into lipid particles. The size of the resulting lipid nanocarriers is influenced by several parameters, including the temperatures of both phases, the tangential flow velocity of the aqueous phase, the lipid phase pressure, and the membrane pore size. This membrane emulsification process offers advantages such as commercial scalability and precise control over particle size by optimizing these parameters, making it suitable for various drug delivery applications[17].

IV. PHARMACOKINETIC VARIATIONS

Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) for topical drug delivery present key pharmacokinetic advantages, optimizing drug entrapment, stability, penetration, and controlled release for active compounds. NLC formulations across various drugs—including quercetin, phenytoin, minoxidil, aceclofenac, ellagic acid (EA), and betamethasone dipropionate (BD)—achieve small particle sizes (ranging from ~117 to 258 nm), which enhance skin permeability and retention, crucial for topical efficacy. High entrapment efficiencies (often exceeding 85%) enable sustained drug release, reducing dosing frequency. NLCs promote a high occlusion effect, increasing skin hydration, thereby enhancing absorption and local retention of the drug, while minimizing systemic exposure. EA-loaded NLCs show improved stability, with an extended shelf-life, pH-sensitive release, and retained antioxidant activity, alongside reduced cytotoxicity for safer skin application. Similarly, BD-loaded NLCs demonstrate significant skin retention, limited systemic absorption, and low irritation potential, supporting localized treatment without adverse effects. Rheological compatibility with hydrogels ensures NLC stability and ease of application. These properties affirm NLCs as versatile and effective vehicles for enhanced therapeutic outcomes in topical drug formulations[18],[19].

V. REGULATORY CONSIDERATIONS

Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLC) are subject to specific regulatory considerations due to their unique properties in drug delivery. Regulatory agencies require comprehensive characterization, including assessments of size, morphology, surface charge (zeta potential), and encapsulation efficiency, along with consistent manufacturing processes to ensure quality and safety. Safety and toxicity evaluations, such as cytotoxicity, immunogenicity, and biodistribution studies, are essential, with long-term toxicity assessments sometimes needed based on the intended use[20]. Stability studies are conducted to ensure NLC integrity over shelf life under various storage conditions. Regulatory pathways for NLC depend on their application (pharmaceuticals, nutraceuticals, or cosmetics), with adherence to guidelines from authorities like the FDA and EMA necessary. Compliance with Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) is crucial for clinical use, ensuring controlled production quality. Biocompatibility is required, particularly for parenteral formulations, and often involves adherence to established biocompatibility standards. For therapeutic applications, clinical trials are mandatory to demonstrate efficacy and safety per Investigational New Drug (IND) requirements. Finally, labelling and claims regarding NLC safety or efficacy must be backed by scientific evidence and conform to regulatory labelling standards[21].

VI. TOXICITY STUDIES

Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) offer a promising solution for topical drug delivery due to their stability, enhanced drug-loading capacity, and improved skin absorption. While generally biocompatible, toxicity remains a concern in clinical applications. Studies indicate that the lipid composition and surfactants significantly influence cytotoxicity. For instance, NLCs formulated with natural oils have shown low cytotoxicity in human epidermal keratinocytes and dermal fibroblasts while effectively inhibiting bacterial growth[22]. Allopurinol-loaded NLCs demonstrated effective drug retention in skin layers

without affecting cell viability, facilitating significant wound healing in vivo[23]. Additionally, research suggests that NLCs are relatively safe for oral delivery due to their biodegradable lipids and low surfactant content, with no observed toxicity in major organs. However, safety profiles vary depending on formulation, lipid composition, and concentration[24]. Overall, while NLCs present advantages such as controlled release and reduced irritation compared to conventional carriers, further investigation into their safety and toxicity is essential, especially concerning interactions between active and inactive ingredients that could exacerbate irritation or toxicity.

TABLE II
PAST RESEARCH WORK OF NLCS FOR TOPICAL DRUG DELIVERY

S.NO	TITLE	DRUG	LIPIDS AND SURFACTANTS USED	METHOD	USES
1.	Development of a topical ointment of betamethasone dipropionate loaded nanostructured lipid carrier	Betamethasone dipropionate	Precirol ATO 5 and OA Tween 80	Melt emulsification with ultra sonication	Atopic dermatitis
2.	Systematic development and characterization of curcumin-loaded nanogel for topical application	Curcumin	Precirol ATO 5 and Capmul MCM Tween 80	High shear homogenisation with Ultrasonication	anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant, anti-microbial, anti-psoriatic, immunomodulatory, wound healing, and anti-cancer
3.	A new topical formulation for psoriasis: Development of methotrexate-loaded nanostructured lipid carriers	Methotrexate	Witepsol S51 Oleic acid Tween 80 Polysorbate 60, P60 Polysorbate 80, P80	High shear homogenisation with Ultra sound technique	Anti-cancer Inhibit the proliferation of cells
4.	Development and evaluation of nanostructured lipid carrier-based hydrogel for topical delivery of 5-fluorouracil	5- Fluorouracil	Precirol® ATO 5 Labrasol® Poloxamer 188	Hot homogenisation method using high pressure homogeniser	Antineoplastic agent used in the topical treatment of a number of diseases, including skin cancers and actinic keratosis
5.	Development and evaluation of Nanostructured Lipid Carrier (NLC) based topical delivery of an anti-inflammatory drug	Aceclofenac	Compritrol 888 ATO PEG-8 Miglyol 812 Polysorbate 80	Modified method of melt ultrasonication and highspeed homogenisation	Anti-inflammatory agent Rheumatoid arthritis Osteoarthritis Anti-pyretic Anti-analgesic
6.	Ellagic Acid Containing Nanostructured Lipid Carriers for Topical Application: A Preliminary Study	Ellagic acid	Tristearin Miglyol Labrasol Poloxamer 188	Hot homogenization and Ultrasonication	Dermal delivery Anti-oxidant
7.	Formulation & characterisation of Nanostructured lipid carrier (NLC) based gel for topical delivery of Etoricoxib	Etoricoxib	Stearic acid Oleic acid Tween 80	Melt emulsification and low temperature solidification method	Inflammation Arthritis Allied conditions
8.	LL37 loaded nanostructured lipid carriers (NLC): A new strategy for the topical treatment of chronic wounds	LL37	Precirol ATO 5 Miglyol 812 N Poloxamer 188 Tween 80	Melt emulsification method	Anti-microbial activity Wound healing Immune response
9.	Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLC) for the Topical Delivery of Lutein	Lutein	Palmitic acid Lipoid S 100 Flora GLO	Solvent injection method	Anti-oxidant
10.	Nanostructured lipid carrier (NLC) based gel of celecoxib	Celecoxib	Stearic acid Oleic acid Poloxamer 188	Micro emulsion technique	Anti-hypertensive agent

11.	Topical Phenytoin Nanostructured Lipid Carriers: Design and Development	Phenytoin	Compritol 888 ATO or Precirol ATO5 Capryol 90 Poloxamer 188 or Tween 80	Hot homogenization and ultrasonication	Anti-epileptic Wound healing
12.	Development of a Quercetin-loaded nanostructured lipid carrier formulation for topical delivery	Quercetin	Glyceryl monostearate Stearic acid Media chain triglyceride	Method of emulsion evaporation-solidification at low temperature	Anti-cancer Anti-oxidation Anti-inflammation dilating coronary arteries Anti-platelet aggregation Anti-anaphylaxis Anti-anemic
13.	Nanostructured lipid carrier system for topical delivery of terbinafine hydrochloride	Terbinafine Hydrochloride	Glyceryl Monostearate Labrasol Pluronic F-127	High pressure homogenisation	Anti-fungal Treats mycoses orally and topically broad activity against dermatophytes, yeast, fungi, molds
14.	Development and evaluation of colloidal modified nano lipid carrier: Application to topical delivery of tacrolimus	Tacrolimus	Glyceryl Trimyristate Propylene glycol monocaprylate Polysorbate 80 (Tween 80) and Sorbitan monooleate (Arlacel 80)	High pressure homogenisation with emulsification	Anti-T-cell drug Suppress inflammation Atopic dermatitis
15.	Design, preparation and in vitro characterizations of fluconazole loaded nanostructured lipid carriers	Fluconazole	Stearic acid Castor oil Tween 20	Ultrasonication emulsification	Antifungal drug for most of the superficial and invasive dermatological conditions
16.	Application of Box–Behnken design for preparation of glibenclamide loaded lipid-based nanoparticles: Optimization, in vitro skin permeation, drug release and in vivo pharmacokinetic study	Glibenclamide	Glyceryl monostearate Capryol™ 90 Tween 80	Emulsion-solvent diffusion and evaporation	Non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus
17.	Voriconazole loaded nanostructured lipid carriers based topical delivery system: QbD based designing, characterization, in-vitro and ex-vivo evaluation	Vorniconazole	Glyceryl monostearate Oleic acid Tween 80 Polyethylene glycol	Hot homogenisation Ultrasonication	Antifungal agent most commonly used in the treatment against infections caused by Candida, Fusarium and Aspergillus
18.	Formulation and evaluation of Nanostructured lipid carriers-based anti-inflammatory for topical drug delivery	Lornoxicam	Precirol ATO-5 Oleic acid Poloxamer 188	Hot High-Pressure homogenisation	Rheumatoid arthritis osteoarthritis
19.	Preparation and characterization of minoxidil loaded nanostructured lipid carrier gel for effective treatment of alopecia	Minoxidil	Oleic acid Tristearin Soya lecithin Tween-80	Melt dispersion ultrasonication method	Alopecia
20.	Development, optimization and evaluation of surfactant-based pulmonary nano lipid carrier system of paclitaxel for the management of drug resistance lung cancer using Box-Behnken design	Paclitaxel	Glyceryl monostearate Oleic acid Tween 20 Tween 80 Tween 60	Emulsification Ultrasonication	Cancer including lung, ovarian, breast, head and neck cancer, and advanced forms of Kaposi's sarcoma

TABLE III
PATENTS

S.N	PATENTS	PATENT NUMBER
1.	Methods of treating inflammatory disorders and global inflammation with compositions comprising phospholipid nanoparticle encapsulations of NSAIDS	US11707436B22
2.	Drug delivery system and methods of treating open angle glaucoma and ocular hypertension	US20140025022A1
3.	Silybin nanostructured lipid carrier and preparation method thereof	CN101632638
4.	Coenzyme Q nanostructured lipid carrier and preparation method thereof	CN101658468
5.	Nanostructured lipid carrier, preparation method, and application thereof	CN101890170
6.	Method for preparing a nanostructured lipid carrier and a product manufactured by the same	KR1020110137263
7.	Resveratrol nanostructured lipid carrier and preparation method thereof	CN102614091
8.	Composite anti-screening agent nanostructured lipid carrier and preparation method thereof	CN102688152
9.	Nanotechnology-based herbal composition for safe and effective treatment of psoriasis	IN422/MUM/2011
10.	Thymoquinone loaded nanostructured lipid carriers (TQ-NLC) and uses thereof	MYPI 2012001818
11.	Nanostructured lipid carrier loaded with phenylethyl resorcinol, preparation method thereof, and cosmetic containing same	CN103860389
12.	Podophyllotoxin preparation resisting condyloma acuminata relapse and HPV latent infection	CN103893167
13.	Quercetin nanostructured lipid carrier and preparation method thereof	CN104172184
14.	Psoralen-doxorubicin-loaded composite nanostructured lipid carrier preparation and preparation method thereof	CN104367549
15.	Nanostructured solid lipid carrier coating vitamin A Palmitate and preparation method thereof	CN10549680
16.	Hydrophilic modification Asiatic acid nanostructured lipid carrier and preparation method thereof	CN105919976
17.	ICAM-1 monoclonal antibody modified simvastatin nanostructured lipid carrier and preparation and application	CN106074389

VII. CONCLUSION

Nanostructured lipid carriers [NLCs] represent an advanced drug delivery systems which are designed to overcome limitations of earlier carriers like Solid Lipid Nanoparticles [SLNs]. The formed NLCs by combining the solid lipid and liquid lipid enhances the drug stability, bioavailability and controlled release. Due to the smaller size of NLCs, it will promote deeper penetration and facilitates both ocular and topical applications. Polymers which are using for the formulation are biodegradable which are safer to use and eco- friendly. To formulate the NLCs, several methods have been discussed for ensuring the adaptability of both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs. Despite all advantages, few challenges arise such as cytotoxicity and lipid stability persist. Overall, NLCs provide a promising platform for efficient, targeted, and sustainable drug delivery with good therapeutic effects.

REFERENCES

1. I. Chauhan, M. Yasir, M. Verma, and A. P. Singh, "Nanostructured lipid carriers: A groundbreaking approach for transdermal drug delivery," *Advanced pharmaceutical bulletin*, vol. 10, no. 2, p. 150, 2020.
2. V.-A. Duong, T.-T.-L. Nguyen, and H.-J. Maeng, "Preparation of solid lipid nanoparticles and nanostructured lipid carriers for drug delivery and the effects of preparation parameters of solvent injection method," *Molecules*, vol. 25, no. 20, p. 4781, 2020.
3. M. Elmowafy and M. M. Al-Sanea, "Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) as drug delivery platform: Advances in formulation and delivery strategies," *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal*, vol. 29, no. 9, pp. 999-1012, 2021.
4. R. Müller, M. Radtke, and S. Wissing, "Nanostructured lipid matrices for improved microencapsulation of drugs," *International journal of pharmaceutics*, vol. 242, no. 1-2, pp. 121-128, 2002.
5. V. N. Thuy, T. V. Van, A. H. Dao, and B.-J. Lee, "Nanostructured lipid carriers and their potential applications for versatile drug delivery via oral administration," *OpenNano*, vol. 8, p. 100064, 2022.
6. A. Czajkowska-Kośnik, M. Szekalska, and K. Winnicka, "Nanostructured lipid carriers: A potential use for skin drug delivery systems," *Pharmacological Reports*, vol. 71, no. 1, pp. 156-166, 2019.
7. B. R. Jasti, W. Abraham, and T. K. Ghosh, "Transdermal and Topical drug delivery systems," in *Theory and practice of contemporary pharmaceutics*: CRC Press, 2021, pp. 423-454.
8. V. Gugleva and V. Andonova, "Recent progress of solid lipid nanoparticles and nanostructured lipid carriers as ocular drug delivery platforms," *Pharmaceutics*, vol. 16, no. 3, p. 474, 2023.
9. F. Tamjidi, M. Shahedi, J. Varshosaz, and A. Nasirpour, "Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLC): A potential delivery system for bioactive food molecules," *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, vol. 19, pp. 29-43, 2013.
10. P. Ghasemiyeh and S. Mohammadi-Samani, "Solid lipid nanoparticles and nanostructured lipid carriers as novel drug delivery systems: Applications, advantages and disadvantages," *Research in pharmaceutical sciences*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 288-303, 2018.
11. E. Gomaa, H. A. Fathi, N. G. Eissa, and M. Elsbahy, "Methods for preparation of nanostructured lipid carriers," *Methods*, vol. 199, pp. 3-8, 2022.
12. M. Cirri *et al.*, "Design, characterization and in vivo evaluation of nanostructured lipid carriers (NLC) as a new drug delivery system for hydrochlorothiazide oral administration in pediatric therapy," *Drug delivery*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 1910-1921, 2018.
13. L. M. Negi, M. Jaggi, and S. Talegaonkar, "Development of protocol for screening the formulation components and the assessment of common quality problems of nano-structured lipid carriers," *International journal of pharmaceutics*, vol. 461, no. 1-2, pp. 403-410, 2014.
14. A. Jintapattanakit, "Preparation of nanoemulsions by phase inversion temperature (PIT) method," *Pharmaceutical Sciences Asia*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 1-12, 2018.
15. V.-A. Duong, T.-T.-L. Nguyen, H.-J. Maeng, and S.-C. Chi, "Preparation of ondansetron hydrochloride-loaded nanostructured lipid carriers using solvent injection method for enhancement of pharmacokinetic properties," *Pharmaceutical Research*, vol. 36, pp. 1-12, 2019.
16. J.-Y. Kwon, M. Khan, and S.-Y. Park, "pH-Responsive liquid crystal double emulsion droplets prepared using microfluidics," *RSC advances*, vol. 6, no. 61, pp. 55976-55983, 2016.
17. A. C. Ortiz, O. Yañez, E. Salas-Huenuleo, and J. O. Morales, "Development of a nanostructured lipid carrier (NLC) by a low-energy method, comparison of release kinetics and molecular dynamics simulation," *Pharmaceutics*, vol. 13, no. 4, p. 531, 2021.
18. X. Kong, Y. Zhao, P. Quan, and L. Fang, "Development of a topical ointment of betamethasone dipropionate loaded nanostructured lipid carrier," *asian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 248-254, 2016.
19. S. Singh Hallan *et al.*, "Ellagic acid containing nanostructured lipid carriers for topical application: A preliminary study," *Molecules*, vol. 25, no. 6, p. 1449, 2020.
20. D. Kebebe *et al.*, "Dimeric c (RGD) peptide conjugated nanostructured lipid carriers for efficient delivery of Gambogic acid to breast cancer," *International Journal of Nanomedicine*, pp. 6179-6195, 2019.
21. T. M. Joseph *et al.*, "Nanoparticles: Taking a unique position in medicine," *Nanomaterials*, vol. 13, no. 3, p. 574, 2023.
22. D. P. de Barros, P. Reed, M. Alves, R. Santos, and A. Oliva, "Biocompatibility and antimicrobial activity of nanostructured lipid carriers for topical applications are affected by type of oils used in their composition," *Pharmaceutics*, vol. 13, no. 11, p. 1950, 2021.
23. C. Varrica, M. Carvalheiro, C. Faria-Silva, C. Eleutério, G. Sandri, and S. Simões, "Topical allopurinol-loaded nanostructured lipid carriers: a novel approach for wound healing management," *Bioengineering*, vol. 8, no. 12, p. 192, 2021.
24. S. Doktorovova, A. B. Kovačević, M. L. Garcia, and E. B. Souto, "Preclinical safety of solid lipid nanoparticles and nanostructured lipid carriers: Current evidence from in vitro and in vivo evaluation," *European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics*, vol. 108, pp. 235-252, 2016.